

EVALUATING CAMEL MILK FOR LIVER PROTECTION IN A DIABETIC RAT MODEL

Zannah Aisha Ibrahim Kolo

Department of Biochemistry, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19234829>

Abstract: Camel milk has long been recognized for its unique biochemical composition and therapeutic potential, particularly its antidiabetic and antioxidant effects. This study was designed to evaluate the hepatoprotective effects of camel milk on liver enzymes in high-fat-diet-induced diabetic Wistar rats. A total of 20 Wistar rats were divided into four groups: Group I (non-diabetic control), Group II (diabetic control), and Groups III and IV (diabetic rats treated orally with camel milk at doses of 2 ml/kg and 4 ml/kg, respectively) for six weeks. Diabetes mellitus was induced using a high-fat diet composed of 10% oil, 20% groundnut meal, and 2% cholesterol.

Biochemical parameters such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), total protein, and albumin were evaluated. Rats treated with camel milk showed significant reductions in ALT, AST, and ALP activities compared to the diabetic group. Notably, AST levels were reduced from 90.2 ± 2.90 IU in the diabetic group to 9.67 ± 1.93 IU and 7.97 ± 1.83 IU in the 2 ml/kg and 4 ml/kg treatment groups, respectively. Similarly, ALP activity declined significantly in treated groups compared to untreated diabetic rats. No significant differences were observed in total protein and albumin levels across all treatment groups.

These findings suggest that camel milk supplementation exerts protective effects on hepatic function by reducing elevated liver enzymes associated with diet-induced type 2 diabetes. The results provide compelling evidence supporting the use of camel milk as a complementary approach in managing hepatic complications of diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: Camel milk, Diabetes Mellitus, Liver Enzymes, Hepatoprotection, Wistar Rats

Introducton

Camel milk is referred to as the white gold of the desert, which contains 11.7 % solids, 3.0 % protein, 3.6 % fat, 0.8 % ash, 4.4 % lactose, 0.13 % acidity and pH of 6.5. The level of sodium, potassium, zinc, iron, copper, magnesium, niacin and vitamin C were higher in the milk with thiamine, riboflavin, folacin, Vitamin B₁₂, pantothenic acid, vitamin A, lysine and

tryptophan (Sawaya et al., 2006). Camel milk possesses microbicidal and immuno-stimulatory properties (Dubey et al, 2016). It contains β - casein of different structural conformations compared to that which is present in cow milk. It also contains high levels of lactoferrin, immunoglobulins, lysozyme and high activity of lactoperoxydase, which are

inflammation-inhibiting proteins that prevent gastrointestinal disorder (Agrawal et al.,

Issue.1 December, 2020.

2005). Camel milk also possesses insulin-like and protective protein used in the treatment of many disease conditions including diabetes mellitus and diarrhoea and it possesses anti-tumour properties (Kula, 2016). Camel milk was demonstrated to be effective in the treatment of type 1 diabetes mellitus (Agrawal et al., 2005). It is a belief in the Middle East that regular consumption of camel milk is beneficial in the prevention and control of diabetes. It was further demonstrated that camel milk contains insulin, which possesses special properties that enhance the absorption of insulin into the circulation easier than insulin from other sources, apparently because the insulin from camel milk is in form of nanoparticles (Ajmaladdin et al., 2012)

Material and Method

Material and Equipment

Camel milk obtained from a nomadic farmer from Chiranchi village in Katsina State, Nigeria. Digital glucometer (Accu-check Active, Boche Diagnostic Company), syringes (sologuard Medical Device P.V.T

Ltd.).

Animals

Twenty (20) Wistar rats of both sexes weighing an average of 170g were used for the experiment. The rats were housed in standard cages, and given access to food and water ad libitum. The cages were kept in the animal house of the Department of Human Physiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The

animals were acclimatised for two weeks before commencement of the experiment.

Diet

Standard animal feeds were used as the control diet and high-fat diet was utilized for the other groups. The cholesterol content in the diet contributed to the inducement of dyslipidaemia. The high-fat diet contains 10% of oil, 20% groundnut mill and 2% cholesterol (Tanko et al., 2016)

Experimental design

The study was conducted for duration of six weeks, during which irrespective of sex, 15 rats were fed with high-fat diet and the remaining five were given normal feed (normal control). Rats were fed with high fat diet and camel milk daily for six weeks after the conformation of type 2 diabetes (blood glucose level > 200 gm/dL).

Groupings

Group 1: (Normal control), Received standard animal feed only
Group 2: (High fat diet group), Received high fat diet only

Group 3: Received high fat diet + 2 ml/kg camel milk orally

Group 4: Received high fat diet + 4 ml/kg camel milk orally

Biochemical assessment/Estimation of Liver enzymes

Each rat was individually anesthetized by exposure to chloroform, followed by a dissection through the thorax using a pair of scissors where by a cardiac puncture was made using a syringe and needle. About 2-4 ml of blood drawn from each rat was divided equally into two parts; one part placed in K⁺ Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid

(heparinized) tubes and another part into plain (non-heparinized) tubes. The tubes were taken to the laboratory for analysis of activities of serum lipid enzymes aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphate (ALT) and alkaline phosphate (ALP) and concentrations of proteins total protein and Albumin.

Estimation of activities of serum liver enzymes

The serum activities of ALP activity was assayed by the method of Basse et al (1946). Serum ALT and AST activities were assayed by the method of Reitman and Frankel (1957). Briefly, the activities were determined using the plasma proteins for analyses by colorimetric method at temperature of 37°C

Statistical analyses

The data obtained were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (mean \pm SEM) and data were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered as significant.

Results

The data presented in Table 1 below shows that there was significant decrease in the activity of aspartate aminotransferase in diabetic rats, administered with camel milk at the dose of 2 ml/kg (9.67 ± 1.93 IU) and at 4 ml/kg (7.97 ± 1.83 IU) when compared to the diabetic group (90.2 ± 2.90 IU). There was no significance difference in alanine aminotransferase in the diabetic rat groups, treated with camel milk of 2 ml/kg (9.04 ± 1.34 IU) when compared to the diabetic control group (7.73 ± 0.98), but the activity was lower ($P < 0.05$) in the diabetic rat group treated with camel milk 4ml/kg (6.48 ± 0.42 IU), when compared with the controls.. Alkaline phosphatase activity was lower (P

< 0.05) in the diabetic rats, administered with camel milk at 2 ml/kg (33.90 ± 3.00 IU) and 4 ml/kg (39.30 ± 8.00 IU) compared respectively to the activity of the enzymes recorded in diabetic controls (117.83 ± 15.70). Levels of Total protein and albumin concentration did not show any significant difference in diabetic rats administered 4 ml/kg (10.80 ± 0.90 IU) and (4.23 ± 0.30 IU) respectively as compared to the diabetic group (10.72 ± 0.82 IU) and (3.85 ± 0.16 IU) respectively but showed slight decrease in total protein level in diabetic rats, treated with camel milk at 2ml/kg (7.93 ± 0.54 IU).

Table 1: Levels of activities of liver enzymes in diabetic Wister rats treated with camel milk

Values are significantly ($P < 0.05$) different. HFD: High fat diet, CM: Camel milk, AST: Aspartate aminotransferase, ALT: Alanine aminotransferase, ALP: Alkaline phosphate, TP: Total phosphate, ALB: Albumin ilk, exerting its effect via binding with β subunit (glycoprotein receptor), which is an insulin-stimulated tyrosine specific protein kinase. The activation of the kinase results in insulin action on glucose metabolism (Kahn, 1985). However, there was a decrease in the level of ALT activity in group treated with camel milk 4ml/kg as compared with the diabetic controls. This finding indicates a reversal effect, restoring the level of ALT activity to normal. The reversal effect could be due to the blockage in the reversible transamination between L-alanine and α -ketoglutarate to form pyruvate and L- glutamate, which plays an important role in gluconeogenesis and amino acid metabolism (Marthur et al. 2016). The findings of this study disagree with those of Makena et al. (2018), who conducted a therapeutic effect of

balanitoside in streptozocin-induced diabetic rats and observed a significant increase in the levels of both AST and ALT activities after treatment. While the findings of Abdelgadir et al. (2015) and Sheweita et al., (2016) both agree with this study. The serum level of ALP activity in this study was decreased significantly in the groups treated with camel milk as compared to the controls. The activity of ALP is highest in the sinusoid and in endothelium of central and peripheral veins, with less concentration in biliary canaliculi (Zafar et al., 2009), and associated with fasting glucose (Bora et al., 2016). The findings disagree with those of Deepika et al. (2016), who reported that elevated levels of ALP activity could be due to excessive deposition of fat in the liver (non-alcoholic fatty liver disease). Chen et al. (2017) found that an increased ALP activity to be an independent risk factor for incident diabetes after controlling other liver-related factors. Nolasco et al. (2015) assessed insulin modulatory effect on liver function in type I diabetes rat model and reported an elevated level of ALP activity in diabetic state; but after treatment with

References

Abdelgadir, E. I. E., Bashier, A. M. K., Al Awadi, F. F., Altinay, A. T., Elsayed, M. A., Khalifa, A. A., Rashid, F., & Makeen, S. (2015). Liraglutide effect on blood pressure, lipids profile and liver enzymes in Arab patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: A prospective LIRA-BPL study. *Journal of Diabetes and Metabolism*, 6, 591. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2155-6156.1000591>

insulin, the levels of ALP level decreased significantly, as recorded in the present study. The decrease could be as a result of the hepatocellular repair of insulin-like effect of camel milk. Further investigation is required to shed more light on the proximate mechanism of anti-diabetic effects of camel milk. It was concluded that camel milk does guard against elevated liver enzymes levels in type 2 diabetes Wistar rats.

Acknowledgements

My immense gratitude to the Almighty for bringing this work to this point. I cannot but appreciate my supervisor in person of Dr. (Mrs.) A. Danborno for judicious looking through my work. My appreciation also goes to Drs. Isa and Jimoh for continuously motivating me to bring this work to light as well as assisting in constituting the diet required for the work. Without the mentoring, guidance and encouragement of Professor J.O. Ayo, this work would not be this finished and presentable. I am immensely grateful, God bless you.

Agrawal, R. P., Beniwal, R., Kochar, D. K., Tuteja, F. C., Ghorui, S. K., Sahani, M. S., & Sharma, S. (2005). Camel milk as an adjunct to insulin therapy improves long-term glycemic control and reduction in doses of insulin in patients with type-I diabetes: A 1-year randomized controlled trial. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 68, 176–177.

Ajamaladdin, M., Al-Senaidy, A., Ewaskizypezak, J., & Jerzy, J. (2012). A study of the anti-

- diabetic agents of camel milk. *International Journal of Molecular Medicine*, 30(3), 585–592.
- Bassey, O. A., Lowery, O. H., & Brock, M. J. (1946). A method for the rapid determination of alkaline phosphatase with five cubic millimetres of serum. *Journal of Biochemistry*, 164, 321–329.
- Bora, K., Borah, M., Chutia, H., Nath, C. K., Das, D., & Ruram, A. A. (2016). Presence of concurrent derangements of liver function tests in type 2 diabetes and their relationship with glycemic status: A retrospective observational study from Meghalaya. *Journal of Laboratory Physicians*, 8(1), 30–35.
- Chen, S. C., Tsai, S. P., Jhao, J., Jiang, W., Tsao, C. K., & Chang, L. (2017). Liver fats, hepatic enzymes, alkaline phosphatase and the risk of incident type 2 diabetes: A prospective study of 132,377 adults. *Scientific Reports*, 7, 4649. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-04631-7>
- Deepika, G., Veeraiyah, N., Naveed, S., & Ramana, M. V. (2016). Serum alkaline phosphatase and high sensitivity C-reactive protein in type II diabetes mellitus: A risk of cardiovascular disease in South Indian population. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*, 4(4), 1107–1114.
- Dubey, U. M., Lal, M., Mittal, A., & Kapur, S. (2016). Therapeutic potential of camel milk. *Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture*, 28(3), 164–176.
- Kahn, C. R. (1985). The molecular mechanism of insulin action. *Annual Review of Medicine*, 36, 429–451. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.me.36.020185.002241>
- Kula, J. (2016). Medicinal values of camel milk. *International Journal of Veterinary Science and Research*, 2(1), 18–25.
- Makena, W., Hamman, W. O., Buraimoh, A. A., Dibal, N. I., & Obaje, S. G. (2018). The therapeutic effects of balanitoside in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Journal of Taibah University Medical Sciences*, 13(4), 402–406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtumed.2018.01.001>
- Mathur, S., Mehta, D. K., Kapoor, S., & Yadav, S. (2016). Liver function in type-2 diabetes mellitus patients. *International Journal of Scientific Study*, 3(10). <https://doi.org/10.17354/ijss/2016/09>
- Nolasco, E. L., Zaroni, F. L., Nunes, F. P., Ferreira, S. S., Freitas, L. A., Silva, M. C., & Martins, J. O. (2015). Insulin modulates liver function in a type I diabetes rat model. *Cell Physiology and Biochemistry*, 36(4), 1467–1479.

Sawaya, W. N., Khalil, J. K., Al-Shalhat, A., & Al-Mohammed, H. (2006). Chemical composition and nutritional quality of camel milk. *Journal of Food Science*, 49(3).

Sheweita, S. A., Mashaly, S., Newairy, A. A., Abdou, H. M., & Eweda, S. M. (2016). Changes in oxidative stress and antioxidants enzyme activities in streptozotocin-induced diabetes mellitus in rats: Role of *Alhagi maurorum* extracts. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, Article 5264064. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/5264064>

Tanko, Y., Jimoh, A., Ahmed, A., Mohammed, A., & Ayo, J. O. (2016). Resveratrol protects rabbits against cholesterol diet-induced hyperlipidaemia. *Nigerian Journal of Physiological Sciences*, 31, 71–75.

Zafar, M., Naeem-ul-Hassan Naqvi, S., Ahmed, M., & Akaimkhani, Z. A. (2009). Altered liver morphology and enzymes in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *International Journal of Morphology*, 27(3), 719–725.